

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D3.11 Report on 5G Infrastructure Setup for CAM final

Document Summary Information

Grant Agreement No	951867	Acronym	5G-ROUTES
Full Title	Report on 5G Infrastructure Setup for CAM final		
Start Date	01/09/2020	Duration	48 months
Project URL	https://www.5g-routes.eu		
Deliverable	D3.11		
Work Package	WP3		
Contractual due date	30 June 2024	Actual submission date	28 June 2024
Nature	Report	Dissemination Level	Public
Lead Beneficiary	TTU		
Responsible Author	Muhammad Mahtab Alam (TTU)		
Contributors	Osama ElGarhi (TTU), Margus Rohtla (TTU), Priit Roosipuu (TTU), Yannick Le Moullec (TTU), Indur Ait (TTU)		
Peer reviewer	Ilba Grillo (AirBus), Arvi Sadam (EEE), David Quesada (ENIDE, Quality Reviewer)		
Additional review on WP1-WP4 deliverables	Kristjan Abakanov (EEE)		

Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
v0.1	02/02/2024	5%	Initial structure and ToC	TTU
V0.5	22/04/2024	70%	First draft (without infrastructure verification)	TTU
V0.9	09/05/2024	93%	Draft for internal review	TTU
V0.92	21/05/2024	95%	Version for internal peer review submission	TTU
V0.95	03/06/2024	96%	Improved version after internal peer review	TTU
V0.96	07/06/2024	97%	Improved version after quality review	TTU
V0.97	11/06/2024	98%	Improved version after internal defence	TTU
V0.99	20/06/2024	99%	Improved version after EC review/feedback June 13-14	TTU
V1.0	28/06/2024	100%	Final version for delivery	TTU

Disclaimer

The content of this document reflects only the author's view. Neither the European Commission nor the INEA are responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

While the information contained in the documents is believed to be accurate, the authors(s) or any other participant in the 5G-ROUTES consortium make no warranty of any kind with regard to this material including, but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose.

Neither the 5G-ROUTES Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be responsible or liable in negligence or otherwise howsoever in respect of any inaccuracy or omission herein.

Without derogating from the generality of the foregoing neither the 5G-ROUTES Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be liable for any direct or indirect or consequential loss or damage caused by or arising from any information advice or inaccuracy or omission herein.

Copyright message

© 5G-ROUTES Consortium. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	7
2	Introduction.....	8
2.1	Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs	8
2.2	Deliverable Overview and Report Structure	9
2.3	Linkage to other Project Outputs.....	9
3	Project architecture for terrestrial ecosystem cross-border field trials.....	11
4	5G Network components for cross-border field trials	15
4.1	User equipment	15
4.2	RAN.....	17
4.3	5G SA Core Network used in the 5G-ROUTES project.....	18
4.3.1	Core capabilities - slicing.....	22
4.3.2	Core capabilities – 5G integrated GNSS RTK Hybrid positioning.	25
4.4	Transport Network and interconnections for 5G cross-border sites.....	27
4.5	5G cross-border sites between Estonia and Latvia (Valga-Valka).....	28
4.5.1	5G site in Estonia (Valga)	28
4.5.2	5G site in Latvia (Valka).....	29
4.6	Additional 5G site in Bikernieki racetrack (Latvia)	30
5	5G cross-border connectivity, coverage and inter-PLMN handover solution: Integration, testing and verification.....	32
5.1	Tests and verification results in the lab	32
5.1.1	Multi-PLMN signal measurement test.....	35
5.1.2	Multi-PLMN Interruption time.....	37
5.1.3	Intra-gNB handover	39
5.2	Tests and verification results from the field-trial site (Valga-Valka).....	41
5.2.1	Cross-border coverage measurements	41
5.2.2	Multi-PLMN interruption time.....	45
5.2.3	Inter-gNB handover results.....	46
6	Conclusions.....	49
7	References.....	50
	Annex I: AT commands response format	51

List of Figures

Figure 1 D3.11 (blue box) linkage to other deliverables.	10
Figure 2 The 5G-ROUTES project architecture.	11
Figure 3 Multi-PLMN solution.	13
Figure 4 Handover procedures. The figure shows the procedure starting from the UE sending its measurement report to the source and target gNBs, till the data is transferred over the target gNB.	14
Figure 5 The 5G NR modem built upon a Quectel RM500Q-GL module.	15
Figure 6 5G SA mobile phones: Nokia XR21 (Left) and XR20 (Right).	16
Figure 7 5G SA mobile phone: Nokia X20.	16
Figure 8 The SIM card for the Latvian side (PLMN code 24701) is on the left, while the one for the Estonian side (PLMN code 24827) is on the right. The PLMN code is written on them.	17
Figure 9 Ericsson BBU.	17
Figure 10 Ericsson RRU.	18
Figure 11. 5G SA core located at TTU premises.	19
Figure 12 The modem is connected over USB to the QCOM utility in order to be configured. See Figure 13 for a zoomed-in screenshot of the QCOM details.	20
Figure 13 Screenshot of the QCOM utility to configure the Quectel 5G modem UE via AT commands.	21
Figure 14 The AMF log shows that the Quectel 5G modem UE is registered and connected to the 5G SA core.	22
Figure 15 SMF log that shows the configured two slices.	25
Figure 16 Positioning ENL platform server (top) at TTU premises.	26
Figure 17 Transport network interconnections with radio and core network for the cross-border 5G-ROUTES project.	27
Figure 20 5G coverage map of the Valga site. The selected site (in black circle) is located at Energia street. The purple line represents the Estonian (right-hand side) - Latvian (left-hand side) border.	28
Figure 21 Telia base station in Valga, Estonia. Telia operates the site and owns its equipment; however, Tele2 Estonia owns the land and the mast.	29
Figure 22 Coverage map of the Valka site where the main beam is pointing toward Valka, Latvia.	30
Figure 23 LMT base station in Valka, Latvia.	30
Figure 24 The coverage Map and the virtual cross-border in the Bikernieki site, Latvia. LMT coverage is in red, while Telia coverage is in blue.	31
Figure 25 TTU 5G SA core lab, including the 5G SA core, BBU, and RRU, as well as eUPF.	33
Figure 26 The BBU and the power supply of the TTU lab.	34
Figure 27 The RRU in TTU lab.	34
Figure 28 Ericsson's IRU in TTU Lab.	35
Figure 29 The radio dot in TTU's lab.	35

Figure 30 The multi-PLMN lab test setup: The orange arrows indicate that the UE is connected to PLMN 24701, whereas the blue arrows indicate that the UE is connected to PLMN 24827. The arrows' directions represent the UE movement. The RSRP value at each step is written above the arrows. 36

Figure 31 Results of multi-PLMN test: (a) RSRP on steps from room 210 (LMT - 24701) to room 212 (TTU - 24827), (b) RSRP on steps from room 212 (TTU - 24827) to room 210 (LMT - 24701), (c) RSRQ on steps from room 210 (LMT - 24701) to room 212 (TTU - 24827), (d) RSRP on steps from room 212 (TTU - 24827) to room 210 (LMT - 24701)..... 36

Figure 32 Average, minimum, and maximum RTT of ping command using the Quectel RM500Q-GL. 37

Figure 33 The RTT of each performed ping command that is measured using the Nemo. 38

Figure 34 Inter-PLMN switching interruption time using the Quectel RM500Q-GL in idle mode. 38

Figure 35 Measured RSRP and interruption time during active session for inter-PLMN switching using Nemo. 39

Figure 36 UE control messages during active session for inter-PLMN switching using Nemo. 39

Figure 37 Handover times from AMF packet capture, both directions. 40

Figure 38 Ran log recorded during the handover test. 41

Figure 39 The part (taken from Figure 38) that shows the handover procedure. The red rectangle is shown in Figure 40 while the blue one is shown in Figure 41. 41

Figure 40 The last measurement report shows that the signal quality of the serving cell is worse than that of the neighbor cell, thus triggering the handover. 41

Figure 41 The serving cell identification number is changed from 1016 to 1018, indicating that the handover has been successful and that the serving cell has been changed..... 41

Figure 42 R&S TSME6 scanner device. 42

Figure 43 R&S ROMES4 measurement software tool used together with the TSME6 scanner. The RSRP of different PCI is measured. 42

Figure 44 Scanner and GPS device antennas..... 43

Figure 45 Measured signal level RSRP of Valga gNB, while driving from Estonia to Latvia. 43

Figure 46 Measured signal level RSRP of Valka gNB, while driving from Latvia to Estonia. 44

Figure 47 Measured signals levels RSRP from both gNBs in a single map view. 44

Figure 48 The cross-border field trial route, from Estonia to Latvia (blue line) and vice-versa (orange line). 45

Figure 49 Average, minimum, and maximum round trip time of ping command using the Quectel RM500Q-GL. 46

Figure 50 AMF logs for HANDOVER messages. 47

Figure 51 RAN log recorded during the handover test 48

List of Tables

Table 1: Adherence to 5G-ROUTES’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.....8

Table 2 Linkage to other project outputs9

Table 3 An example of a slice configuration (in this example eMBB SST=1 is depicted). 23

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used.

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AT	Attention Commands
CAM	Connected Automated Mobility
BBU	Base Band Unit
CNIS	Cloud-Native Infrastructure
CUPS	Control plane and User Plane Separation
DNN	Data Network Name
ENL	Ericsson Network Location
IRU	Indoor Radio Unit
K8s	Kubernetes cluster
MBH	Mobile Backhaul
MCC	Mobile Country Code
MNC	Mobile Network Code
NR	New Radio
NSA	Non-Stand Alone
NUC	Next Unit of Computing
PA	Project Architecture
PDU	Packet Data Unit
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
RRU	Remote Radio Unit
SD	Service Differentiator
S-NSSAI	Single – Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
SST	Slice Service Type
SA	Stand Alone
UC	Use Case
UE	User Equipment
VLAN	Virtual LAN

1 Executive Summary

The scope of deliverable D3.11 is to present the final Project Architecture (PA) and to describe and summarize the 5G infrastructure setup for Connected Automated Mobility (CAM) in the 5G-ROUTES project. The report is a final version: that is, it describes the PA in its final form and the final infrastructure information, which is used in field trials at the cross-border corridor (“Via Baltica North”). In terms of infrastructure, the report describes the final implemented solution while referring to or updating the solutions and information described in intermediate deliverable D3.1.

Contrary to what was assumed at the beginning of the 5G-ROUTES project, the current commercially available 5G technology is not mature enough to conduct the 5G Stand Alone (SA) cross-border field trials, particularly in terms of roaming (formal roaming is not available in the used small target core from the vendor side). Moreover, 5G SA core is not available in any commercial networks in Estonia, as per most of the mobile network operators’ timeline this will be deployed during 2025 (latest). Therefore, a technical solution, named the “Inter-PLMN,” was chosen and adopted as a workaround to conduct large-scale field trials, where PLMN stands for Public Land Mobile Networks. The Inter-PLMN is widely used by most of the related EU projects (H2020 Cross-border) and also CEF projects. It offers very lower delays for the cross-border solution compared to the formal roaming solutions. It is expected that the inter-PLMN-based and local breakout solutions will be widely used for border-crossing projects. In this solution, virtual PLMNs are created to represent different MNOs, and roaming is performed between them, similar to the local breakout in conventional networks.

As part of task T3.1, the relevant 5G infrastructure was installed and configured. The 5G SA core was upgraded to Version TS1.2. During the trials, the 5G infrastructure is arranged as the following:

- The 5G core is located in TTU premises.
- Two 5G base stations are located in Valga and Valka (one each) to cover the border crossing for vehicles.
- Bikernieki has been used as the site for earlier 5G-NSA trials. As for the final field trials, Bikernieki could potentially be used for the automated driving Use Cases (UCs) with 5G- SA network.

The 5G core (i.e. small EEE 5G SA core) is located, owned, and operated by TTU. In Estonia, the site in Valga is operated by Telia, and the radio elements are supplied and configured by EEE. On the Latvian side (i.e., the Valka site), the site is owned and operated by LMT, whereas the radio elements are supplied and configured by EEE. Regarding Bikernieki, one of the base stations in is owned and operated by Telia, while the other is owned and operated by LMT. Given that Ericsson is the sole supplier of the radio equipment in the project, there are no interoperability issues in this regard. The primary interoperability issue is between the User Equipment (UE) devices and the 5G SA core, i.e., connecting mobile phones to the 5G SA core.

Next, the integration and readiness of the network are verified by testing and verifying the 5G cross-border connectivity, coverage, and inter-PLMN handover solution, first in a lab environment (signal measurement tests and slicing tests) and then from the field trial site (Valga-Valka).

In summary, this deliverable provides the description and verification of the infrastructure used in the terrestrial field trials. It covers the final project technical architecture that includes the inter-PLMN solution, as well as the different infrastructure network components (user equipment, RAN, 5G SA core, transport network, and the sites overview).

2 Introduction

The objective of 5G-ROUTES project is to conduct 5th generation connected and automated mobility cross-border trials in designated 5G cross-border corridor (“Via Baltica North”). These advanced cross-border large scale field trials are conducted to validate the 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions. The aim of these tests is to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CAM ecosystems and related services in digitized motorways throughout Europe. The scope of deliverable D3.11 is to describe the network PA, the 5G infrastructure setup for CAM in 5G-ROUTES project, and to verify the readiness of the infrastructure.

2.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map 5G-ROUTES’s Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to 5G-ROUTES’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D3.11 Report on 5G Infrastructure Setup for CAM (final)	Report on 5G Infrastructure Setup for CAM (final)	Sections 3-5	Description and verification of the infrastructure used in the large-scale field trials.
TASKS			
T3.1 Installation, setup and configuration of 5G infrastructure including seamless integration between terrestrial and satellite 5G	Project architecture and inter-PLMN solution	Section 3	The final project technical architecture that includes the inter-PLMN solution is presented.
	In this task the relevant 5G infrastructure are installed and configured. The task presents the 5G field trial network infrastructure.	Section 4	The different infrastructure network components are presented. Namely, the user equipment, RAN, 5G SA core, transport network, and the sites overview.
	Testing and verification	Section 5	The network readiness is verified by collecting base metrics such as delay. Particularly, the verification is first performed in the lab to measure the inter-PLMN switching delay. Then, the measurements are repeated in the field to verify that the network is ready for the cross-border field trials.

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The remaining of the deliverable is organized as follows.

- Section 3 presents the final technical PA with the inter-PLMN solution.
- Section 4 lists the different infrastructure components, that is, the core, transport, and RAN.
- Section 5 demonstrates the network readiness through providing the testing and verification results.
- Finally, Section 6 concludes the deliverable.

2.3 Linkage to other Project Outputs

Table 2 Linkage to other project outputs

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	Contribution and Value of linkage
D1.10 Report on 5G-ROUTES CAM deployment plan and longer-term deployment strategies	The report provided the potential infrastructure elements, trial locations, frequencies, and standard specifications
D2.1 AI Assisted Cross-Domain MEC & Integration Fabric CAM Services v1.0	The first version of the PA is presented in D2.1.
D3.1 Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM	The direct predecessor to this deliverable. The sites' locations and components were presented in D3.1.
D3.4 Report on CAM infrastructure development v2.0	Provides the CAM infrastructure, that is, the required hardware, software, and CAM service backend to fulfil different CAM UC scenarios.
D3.7 Report on Integration of Technological Enablers with MNO Infra v0.1	Integration related to the CAM service platform and technological enablers, that is, integration with use cases, with 5G SA network and with UE.
D4.1 Use Cases' field trials planning, setup and operational management handbook	Establishes and evaluate the methodologies for testing, validating, and benchmarking the validation for UCs through the field trials.

D3.11 takes input from D1.10 and its predecessor D1.3. These deliverables provide the technical framework, including the available spectrum and the 3GPP standard specifications that are used for the infrastructure used in the trials. Moreover, assessments of the field trials' locations, suitable infrastructure, and deployment plans are provided in these deliverables. Note that T1.2 ended in M38, due to LMT leaving the consortium. Updates to the work described in D1.10, such as the future long-term strategies are reported in D3.11.

The first version of the PA is extracted from D2.1. This version is modified and updated to include the most suitable technical solutions that are needed to conduct the trials.

The direct predecessor of D3.11 is D3.1 that includes the full details about the trial sites as well as the predicted rollout methodology and roadmap.

Moreover, from WP3, D3.4 and D3.7 complement D3.11. D3.4 presents the infrastructure from the CAM point of view, that is, the components (infrastructure) that are needed by the vehicle to conduct the trials such as the

OBU. D3.7 presents the integration of the CAM service platform with the network infrastructure; hence, it has to be in line with the proposed PA and technical solutions because the integration is performed in the network itself, for example, with the inter-PLMN.

Once the infrastructure is ready, this deliverable D3.11 is used by D4.1 to tailor the necessary tests and validation scenarios used in the field trials.

Figure 1 D3.11 (blue box) linkage to other deliverables.

3 Project architecture for terrestrial ecosystem cross-border field trials

In this section, we start by presenting the PA and then we provide details about the inter-PLMN technical solution. With regards to the PA, we specifically provide the main modifications and changes that were applied to the previous version documented in D2.1.

Figure 2 The 5G-ROUTES project architecture.

At the mobile infrastructure level, the 5G-ROUTES PA considers the 5G New Radio (NR) SA core network products from Ericsson hosted in Tallinn by TTU. The general description of the 5G SA core can be found in D2.1. Moreover, a description of the different 5G network components and a comparison of 5G SA vs NSA architecture is presented in D1.10. In D2.5, the operation of these 5G network nodes is described in the context of positioning. The 5G NR SA core network is 3GPP Rel. 15 compliant with selected Rel. 16 capabilities.

Several modifications have been made to the PA (that was presented in D2.1). In the previously accepted deliverable, there were two 5G SA cores whereas in this version there is only one 5G SA core. The consortium had to use one 5G SA core deployed by TTU (with two virtual cores instances components, please see details below). One of the main reasons for the modifications is the unavailability of some core functionalities (e.g., 5G

SA roaming is not available during the lifetime of the project for the small target core). To be able to perform cross-border trials with one core, an inter-PLMN technical solution is used to allow the demonstration of PLMN (e.g., mobile network operator) switching/handover across the border. Note that with a single core, we aim to show how UEs can roam (cross-border) from one country to another (which is the main objective of the project); nonetheless, in the used 5G service-based architecture, there are internal failover mechanism as the network functions are virtualized, and if failure happens then the network can rapidly recover.

In this solution, PLMNs are created in the core and connected to physical RAN sites on the Estonian-Latvian border (Valga-Valka). Figure 2 shows the final PA of the 5G-ROUTES project. In the figure, the main modifications can be observed. The current solution comprises one core network (located at TTU). The two PLMNs (that represent Estonia and Latvia) share most of the physical core network functions, such as Access and Mobility Management (AMF) and Session Management Function (SMF), whereas virtual network functions, such as the Unified Data Management (UDMs), are created for each PLMN. As for the User plane function (UPF), within the 5G-ROUTES project, one UPF in the core is used with one PLMN, whereas an edge UPF is used with the other PLMN at the site near the border (the integration of the edge UPF with 5G network and CAM platform and its results will be documented in D3.7). For the RAN part, each PLMN has a dedicated RAN. Note that in Figure 2, some instances are identified as virtual (such as the vUPF), which means that these nodes are not shared. PLMN-A serves domain 1, and PLMN-B serves domain 2. In the following, we provide more details on the inter-PLMN solution.

It is worth mentioning that the inter-PLMN solution is not an unknown solution that was introduced in the 5G-ROUTES project to overcome the cross-border demonstration issue. Inter-PLMN has been discussed in other European projects, such as 5GMOBIX [1], tested in projects, such as 5GCroCo [2], and discussed in the 3GPP standard specification [3]. Moreover, it offers several advantages. It facilitates field and lab trials, especially for small players, which can lead to an increase in research, more competition, and less monopoly by the big players. For example, in the 5G-ROUTES project, TTU, although not a mobile network operator, was able to conduct lab trials on its premises. Moreover, it facilitated field trials because only partial involvement of the mobile network operators was needed (the RAN using the RAN of the mobile operators in the field) and field trials (using the RAN of the mobile operators in the field).

The inter-PLMN solution is used in the 5G-ROUTES project to enable the testing of the inter-operator cross-border handover. The inter-PLMN solution is possible because of the multi-PLMN network functionality. In this part we introduce the concept of multi-PLMN and then we present the inter-PLMN handover. A PLMN is identified by a globally unique PLMN code, which consists of a Mobile Country Code (MCC) and Mobile Network Code (MNC). In the 5G-ROUTES project, the unique code for LMT is 24701 and for TTU is 24827.

The multi-PLMN enables the core (e.g., AMF) to support up to 12 NR PLMNs. An illustration of the multi-PLMN solution is shown in Figure 3, where two PLMNs (PLMN A, and PLMN B) are deployed. It can be observed from the figure that the multi-PLMN is flexible in the sense that network functions such as AMF, SMF, and NRF can host multiple PLMNs. These PLMNs can be deployed in network functions at various locations in the network, or in just one location. The RAN can also support one or more PLMNs. In Figure 3, a brief operation of the inter-PLMN handover is illustrated, where a UE served by PLMN A must perform a handover once it moves from its coverage area to the coverage area of PLMN B.

Figure 3 Multi-PLMN solution.

The multi-PLMN does not cause any performance degradation, nor does it have any impact on the network's performance metrics, such as throughput, signaling capacity, CPU load, or memory consumption.

Inter-PLMN handover can be performed between two NG-RANs sharing the same core, given that each belongs to a different PLMN. The procedures are shown in Figure 3.

In Figure 3, once a UE leaves the Source coverage area (i.e. PLMN A's NG-RAN) and approaches the Target coverage area (i.e. PLMN B's NG-RAN), the handover request procedures initiate. Then the procedure illustrated in Figure 4 are performed:

- The UE is sending measurement reports to its serving gNB ("source gNB", i.e. PLMN A's NG-RAN in Figure 3).
- Based on the configurations, once the source gNB detects that the UE needs to be handed over to another gNB ("target gNB", i.e. PLMN B's NG-RAN in Figure 3), it makes a handover decision.
- The source gNB sends a handover request to the target gNB and once it is accepted, the handover execution commences.
- The handover is triggered once the source gNB sends an RRCReconfiguration message to the UE.
- The source gNB starts status transfer and buffers the UE data (to be forwarded to the target gNB).
- To connect to the target gNB, the UE performs a random-access procedure.
- Once the connection is established, the UE sends an RRCReconfigurationComplete message to the target gNB.

- The Target RAN sends a path switch request to the AMF to change the data-control path of the Packet Data Unit (PDU) session of the UE.
- The AMF sends the request to update the UE PDU's session information on a NSMF_PDUSession_UpdateSMContext message request to the SMF along with the UE location information and the SMF responds to the AMF.
- Then, the SMF either declines the request, which results in a path switch request failure, or grants the path switch request, which leads the AMF to respond to the path switch request with an acknowledgement.
- The source gNB releases the UE resources, and the UE is now served by the target gNB.

7

Figure 4 Handover procedures. The figure shows the procedure starting from the UE sending its measurement report to the source and target gNBs, till the data is transferred over the target gNB.

4 5G Network components for cross-border field trials

The purpose of this section is to elaborate on the various 5G network components and the infrastructure that are used in the 5G-ROUTES project. These components comprise: 1. user equipment (UE) devices, 2. radio access network (RAN) elements, 3. core network, and 4. transport network. These are introduced in Subsections 4.1 to 4.4, respectively. Moreover, Subsection 4.5 introduces the 5G cross-border sites in Estonia (Valga) and Latvia (Valka), and Subsection 4.6 introduces the additional 5G site in Bikernieki.

4.1 User equipment

There are three main types of UEs used for testing the 5G network, i.e. 5G NR modems, 5G routers, and 5G mobile phones; this is not an exhaustive list of the UEs (additional UEs will be used in the field trials). SIM cards are prepared by the TTU for the 5G-ROUTES project, to be used with the UEs.

The 5G NR modem is built upon the Quectel RM500Q-GL module [1], which is shown in Figure 5. It is designed for the 5G sub 6 GHz operation. It supports 5G SA and NSA. It also supports MIMO (4 x 4 in the downlink and 2 x 2 in the uplink). As for the maximum 5G SA data rates, the modem supports downlink data rate of up-to 2.1 Gbps, and uplink data rate of up-to 900 Mbps.

Figure 5 The 5G NR modem built upon a Quectel RM500Q-GL module.

As for the mobile phones, they should support 5G SA network. Several mobile phones were tested and worked with both PLMNs, such as the Nokia XR21, XR20, and XR20, which are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7.

Figure 6 5G SA mobile phones: Nokia XR21 (Left) and XR20 (Right).

Figure 7 5G SA mobile phone: Nokia X20.

Two types of SIM cards are prepared (programmed) and used. The first type is for the Latvian side, that is SIM cards with PLMN code 24701, where 247 is the MCC which is the country code of Latvia, and 01 is the MNC which is the network code of LMT. The second type is for the Estonian side, that is SIM cards with PLMN code 24827, where 248 is the MCC which is the country code of Estonia, and 27 is the MNC which is the network code of TTU. Examples of the SIM cards are presented in Figure 8. TTU has prepared 15 SIM cards for the project.

Figure 8 The SIM card for the Latvian side (PLMN code 24701) is on the left, while the one for the Estonian side (PLMN code 24827) is on the right. The PLMN code is written on them.

4.2 RAN

The radio access network comprises a Base Band Unit (BBU), and Remote Radio Unit (RRU). A BBU can be connected to multiple RRUs. The BBUs and RRUs used in the 5G-ROUTES project (all sites use the same model for both BBU and RRU) are from Ericsson. The BBU is shown in Figure 9, the model is Baseband 6648 and supports up to 10000 users, with a maximum data rate of 15 Gbps and 3 Gbps in the downlink and uplink, respectively, and up to 12 radio interfaces for the radio units. The RRU, shown in Figure 10, model AIR 3268 B78Y, is a TDD antenna integrated radio unit that supports 3450-3800MHz, with 32 transmitters and receivers with 200 W output power and 128 antenna elements. The Instantaneous Bandwidth (IBW) is 200 MHz; it has a 16/8 Downlink/uplink layer multi-user MIMO.

Figure 9 Ericsson BBU.

Figure 10 Ericsson RRU.

4.3 5G SA Core Network used in the 5G-ROUTES project.

The 5G SA core network is located in TTU premises (coordinates: 59.39464404781739, 24.671724661573958).

The 5G SA core (presented in Figure 11) solution is provided by Ericsson and is based on Target Solution 5G Dual-Mode Core Small (TS DMC Small) which is dual mode capable (including both 5G and EPC Network Functions); but for this project only the functionality of 5GC (SA mode) is required and is deployed. The 5G SA Core solution is deployed on Cloud-Native Infrastructure (CNIS) platform in TTU Lab.

Figure 11. 5G SA core located at TTU premises.

To verify that a UE can be connected to the 5G SA core, the following test to register and connect our Quectel 5G modem to the 5G SA core has been performed.

The Quectel 5G modem is set up using the QCOM software, which is provided by Quectel. The setup is done using Attention (AT) commands. AT Commands are commands that are typically used to configure IoT devices. The AT commands are entered in the QCOM and transmitted to the modem to configure it. In Figure 12, we show the modem connected to the PC and the QCOM software. In Figure 13, we show a screenshot of the QCOM. Finally, Figure 14 shows that the UE (Modem) is connected to the 5G SA core.

Figure 12 The modem is connected over USB to the QCOM utility in order to be configured. See Figure 13 for a zoomed-in screenshot of the QCOM details.

Figure 13 Screenshot of the QCOM utility to configure the Quectel 5G modem UE via AT commands.

```

Subscriber Data
-----
IMSI : 248270000000003
Mobile Subscriber ISDN No. :
IMEI : 863305041249940
Radio Access Technology : NGRAN
Mobility Management State : RM-REGISTERED CM-CONNECTED
UE Time Zone
  time offset : GMT + 3 hour(s) 0 minute(s)
  daylight saving time : 1 hour(s) adjustments
Time of Registration in AMF : 2023-10-03 14:26:51.352+03:00
Time released :
RAT restrictions : [WLAN]
Forbidden areas : []
Core network type restrictions : Information not available
RFSF Index in Use : 1
Service area restriction
  Restriction type : NOT_ALLOWED_AREAS
  TACs : []
  Max num. of TAs : Information not available
Subscribed UE Usage Type : 0
AMF UE NGAP Id : 6394620680
RAN UE NGAP Id : 16793637
NAS Uplink Count : 10
NAS Downlink Count : 12
Security Context State : Security Context with Secure exchange
UE Security Capability
  NPS Encryption Algorithms : nea0, nea1_128, nea2_128, nea3_128
  NPS Integrity Algorithms : nia1_128, nia2_128, nia3_128
  EPS Encryption Algorithms :
  EPS Integrity Algorithms :
SGMM Capability : sl_mode_not_supported
In MICO Mode : No
CN Assistance Info RRC INACTIVE to NG-RAN : false
Paging Proceed Flag : Set
Last Visited Tracking Area [TAI] : 248-27-5000
Tracking Area List : 248-27-5000
Latest NG-RAN Node List (MCC-MNC-Size-gNBId) : 248-27-22-1
IMS VoPS : Not supported
SMS over NAS Allowed : false
SMSF Instance ID : Information not available
SMSF Service Instance ID :
Subscribed S-NSSAIs
  Default S-NSSAIs : 1,2
  Non Default S-NSSAIs :
Registered S-NSSAIs : 1,2
Requested S-NSSAIs : 1,2
Rejected S-NSSAIs :
SG-GUTI
  PLMN Id : 248-27
  AMF Region Id : 255
  AMF Set Id : 2
  AMF Pointer : 13
  SG-TMSI : 4026583370 (#F000C94A)
  
```

UE is registered and connected.

Figure 14 The AMF log shows that the Quectel 5G modem UE is registered and connected to the 5G SA core.

4.3.1 Core capabilities - slicing

The core can be configured to support various network slices. For the 5G-ROUTES project, two slices are configured, one is an eMBB slice to support UCs that require high bandwidth, such as Brainstorm’s gaming UC. The second is a default slice (best effort). URLLC is supported by the core network; however, end-to-end URLLC slice implementation is not prioritized since eMBB slice can also satisfy the service requirements. As an example, in Table 3 we present the udmSliceProfile configuration file of the eMBB network slice as defined in the UDM of the 5G core network, where we can see the slice parameters we use.

Table 3 An example of a slice configuration (in this example eMBB SST=1 is depicted).

```

{
  "udmSliceProfileId": "1",
  "plmnIdSets": [
    {
      "plmnIdSetIdentifier": "Default",
      "nssai": {
        "defaultSingleNssais": [
          {
            "nssai": {
              "sst": 1
            },
            "dnnListId": "Default"
          }
        ]
      },
      "dnnLists": [
        {
          "dnnListId": "Default",
          "dnnDataList": [
            {
              "sscModes": {
                "defaultSscMode": "SSC_MODE_1",
                "allowedSscModes": [
                  "SSC_MODE_2",
                  "SSC_MODE_3"
                ]
              },
              "charging3gppCharacteristics": "0000",
              "defaultDnnIndicator": true,
              "qos5gProfile": {
                "qi5": 8,
                "arp": {
                  "priorityLevel": 1,
                  "preemptCap": "NOT_PREEMPT",
                  "preemptVuln": "NOT_PREEMPTABLE"
                },
                "priorityLevel": 80
              },
              "sessionAmbr": {
                "uplink": "1000 Gbps",
                "downlink": "1000 Gbps"
              },
              "upSecurity": {
                "upIntegr": "PREFERRED",
                "upConfid": "PREFERRED"
              },
              "lboRoamingAllowed": false,

```



```

Smf Selection Subscription Data
-----
S-NSSAI 1
  DNN                               : internet1.taltech.ee
  Default DNN Indicator              : true
S-NSSAI 2
  DNN                               : internet2.taltech.ee
  Default DNN Indicator              : true

Subscribed DNN Configuration
-----
Associated PDU Session IDs          : 1
DNN                                : internet1.taltech.ee

Subscribed DNN Configuration
-----
Associated PDU Session IDs          : 2
DNN                                : internet2.taltech.ee

Active PDU Session
-----
Id                                  : 1
S-NSSAI                             : 1
DNN requested                       :
DNN in use                          : internet1.taltech.ee
Active EPS Bearer IDs               :
SMF in use
  Instance ID                       : d67766fc-210f-4ecf-858f-cc42a60fc00e
  IPv4                              : 172.22.200.96
  IPv6                              :
  FQDN                              : Information not available

Active PDU Session
-----
Id                                  : 2
S-NSSAI                             : 2
DNN requested                       : internet2.taltech.ee
DNN in use                          : internet2.taltech.ee
Active EPS Bearer IDs               :
SMF in use
  Instance ID                       : d67766fc-210f-4ecf-858f-cc42a60fc00e
  IPv4                              : 172.22.200.96
  IPv6                              :
  FQDN                              : Information not available
    
```

UE has been created in two slices

Figure 15 SMF log that shows the configured two slices.

4.3.2 Core capabilities – 5G integrated GNSS RTK Hybrid positioning.

One of the capabilities that is tested in the 5G-ROUTES project is the utilization of the 5G integrated hybrid RTK-GNSS to provide high accuracy positioning. Ericsson Network Location (ENL) is installed and integrated with the 5G SA core at TTU to provide high accuracy positioning service.

Figure 16 shows the positioning ENL platform servers, above the 5G SA core servers. More detailed information about the positioning service and its performance and integration with the use cases is provided in D2.5 Positioning Enhancements for V2X and in the final deliverable to-be-submitted (deliverable D2.4 Slicing and Positioning Technologies for CAM services in Cross-Border Environment).

Figure 16 Positioning ENL platform server (top) at TTU premises.

4.4 Transport Network and interconnections for 5G cross-border sites.

The 5G-ROUTES project’s cross-border *terrestrial network* is connected via optical cables. There are four main sites:

- In Estonia, there are 1) the Valga site (operated by Telia), and 2) the TTU site.
- In Latvia, there are 3) the Valka site (operated and owned by LMT), and 4) the Bikernieki site (contains base stations for Telia and LMT).

The transport network is presented in Figure 17. The 5G SA core site is located in TTU, all the other sites represent the access part, that is the gNBs are placed in these sites. Moreover, the Valga site has an edge UPF (eUPF) in addition to a CAM platform point of presence.

Figure 17 Transport network interconnections with radio and core network for the cross-border 5G-ROUTES project.

The Valga site comprises the RAN (RRU and BBU), an eUPF (for illustration purpose we assume that the eUPF is placed in Valga; however, it can also be placed in Valka, as mentioned in Section 3), and the CAM platform (reachable through the MikroTik router). These components are reachable through the fiber Mobile Backhaul (MBH) in Valga. They are connected to the same port on the switch; however, each of them belongs to a different Virtual LAN (VLAN). The transport connection to this site is based on fiber optical connections rented from Elisa. The Valka site contains LMT’s RAN, the transport network is connected through Pērses Iela. The 5G SA core is placed in TTU; there are two MikroTik routers serving the virtual UPF, which realizes the multi-PLMN

functionality. Additionally, a point of presence of the CAM platform is placed in the TTU site. The transport connection to TTU is implemented through an optical MBH switch and TTU’s network VSP 700 switch. The optical connections of the three sites are connected in Telia’s IP transport network. Note that in case the Bikernieki site will be used, then the Bikernieki site and the Valka site will share the same optical transport network to Pērses Iela.

4.5 5G cross-border sites between Estonia and Latvia (Valga-Valka)

This part provides updated information about the sites in Estonia and Latvia, that is the Valga and the Valka sites, respectively. The information describing the sites in Valga-Valka was first provided in deliverable D3.1 Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM. Although most of this information is still valid for the Valga site (Telia operates the site and owns its equipment; however, Tele2 Estonia owns the land and the mast) and the Valka site (owned by LMT), the modifications to that information are presented in this section. To note that both sites use Ericsson equipment (e.g., base band units and radio units).

4.5.1 5G site in Estonia (Valga)

All information regarding the Valga site, such as maps, coordinates, and information regarding the site location, is presented in the deliverable D3.1 Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM in Section 4.2. This deliverable D311 reports modifications and additions to this information.

- The bandwidth is 65 MHz, and the frequency band is n78 (range 3477,5 MHz - 3542,5 MHz).
- The site is rented from Telia.
- The coverage map and the picture of the site are shown in Figure 18 and Figure 19, respectively.

Figure 18 5G coverage map of the Valga site. The selected site (in black circle) is located at Energia street. The purple line represents the Estonian (right-hand side) - Latvian (left-hand side) border.

Figure 19 Telia base station in Valga, Estonia. Telia operates the site and owns its equipment; however, Tele2 Estonia owns the land and the mast.

4.5.2 5G site in Latvia (Valka)

All information regarding the Valka site, such as maps, coordinates, and information regarding the site location, is presented in the deliverable D3.1 Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM in Section 4.2. This deliverable reports modifications and additions to this information.

- The bandwidth is 25 MHz, and the frequency band is n78 (range 3,75 GHz - 3,775 GHz).
- The site is rented from LMT.
- Ericsson has provided LMT with AIR 6449 B79A and AIR 3268 B78Y antennas. LMT has obtained the license to use them.
- The coverage map and the picture of the site are shown in Figure 20 and Figure 21, respectively.

Figure 20 Coverage map of the Valka site where the main beam is pointing toward Valka, Latvia.

Figure 21 LMT base station in Valka, Latvia.

4.6 Additional 5G site in Bikernieki racetrack (Latvia)

All information regarding the Bikernieki site, such as maps, coordinates, and information regarding the site location, is presented in the deliverable D3.1 Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM in Section 4.1. This deliverable reports modifications and additions to this information. As needed this potential site can be used for automated driving use cases.

The Bikernieki site (Figure 22) comprises a Telia gNB with the same setup as the Valga site that is presented in Section 4.5.1 of this deliverable, and an LMT gNB with the same setup as the Valka site that is presented in Section 4.5.2 of this deliverable.

Figure 22 The coverage Map and the virtual cross-border in the Bikernieki site, Latvia. LMT coverage is in red, while Telia coverage is in blue.

5 5G cross-border connectivity, coverage and inter-PLMN handover solution: Integration, testing and verification.

An essential goal of this deliverable is to verify that the infrastructure, especially the inter-PLMN technical solution, is working. Therefore, the purpose of this section is to verify that the inter-PLMN handover is working in two domains for cross-border connectivity. The section is split into two parts. The first one is to show lab verification tests and logs. The second part is to verify that the infrastructure is operational and functioning correctly in the actual field sites. Note that there are differences between the setup of the infrastructure in the lab and the field. One key difference is that in the lab only one BBU is used that is connecting the two RRUs (one RRU represents TTU-Estonia and the other represents LMT-Latvia).

The following tests are performed:

- Two PLMN operation and coverage test – at TTU lab,
- RTT ping test to assess the delay – at TTU lab,
- Interruption time measurements when switching the PLMN (active and idle modes) – at TTU lab,
- Intra-gNB handover interruption time – at TTU lab,
- Two PLMNs operation and coverage test – at the Valga-Valka field,
- RTT ping test to assess the delay – at the Valga-Valka field.
- Inter-gNB tests results – at the Valga-Valka field.

5.1 Tests and verification results in the lab

This part provides the lab verification test results. The 5G test is performed in TTU. Figure 23 shows the server room in which the 5G SA core, BBU, and RRU are located. The BBU (in TTU) and its power supply are shown in Figure 24. A BBU can be connected to multiple RRUs. For the lab test of the 5G-ROUTES project, there are two radio connections. The first one is connected to the RRU of Figure 25, which also contains the antenna. The second one is connected to an Indoor Radio Unit (IRU) shown in Figure 26, which is connected to the radio dot antenna in Figure 27 (which is placed in a different room to enable the multi-PLMN); the IRU in an intermediary between the BBU and the dot antenna. The two radios are needed to create two cells to be able to test the inter-PLMN solution and the handover.

Figure 23 TTU 5G SA core lab, including the 5G SA core, BBU, and RRU, as well as eUPF.

Figure 24 The BBU and the power supply of the TTU lab.

Figure 25 The RRU in TTU lab.

Figure 26 Ericsson's IRU in TTU Lab.

Figure 27 The radio dot in TTU's lab.

5.1.1 Multi-PLMN signal measurement test

In this part, we demonstrate that the multi-PLMN based network at TTU is working, and we measure the coverage. Specifically, we show that there are two PLMNs, each has its own coverage, and we calculate the delay incurred by each PLMN. Note that the output power level of the radio units has been adjusted (decreased) to be suitable for indoor operation within the lab premises.

The goal of the first test is to show the signal power change as we move away from the radio unit serving one PLMN to the radio unit serving the other PLMN, and to identify the coverage of each PLMN. The First PLMN represents LMT and is located in room 210; the other PLMN represents TTU and is located in room 212. The floor layout and location of the PLMNs is shown in Figure 28.

The test was performed using the 5G Quectel RM500Q-GL module (presented in Chapter 4) and using the AT commands (presented in that same chapter).

AT command `AT+QENG="servingcell"` was used to measure the identity and the signals of serving cell. The possible responses of this AT command are reported in Annex 1.

The distance in corridor between rooms 210 (LMT: cellID 43F8 – PLMN 24701) and 212 (TTU: cellID=43FA - PLMN 24827) is 12 meters, which can be covered by 10 human steps. Room doors were closed. Test command (AT+QENG="servicell") was run at each human step. Tests were performed on 28.04.2024 at 8:38-9:07. The results show the measured Reference Signals Received Power (RSRP) and Reference Signal Received Quality (RSRQ).

Figure 28 The multi-PLMN lab test setup: The orange arrows indicate that the UE is connected to PLMN 24701, whereas the blue arrows indicate that the UE is connected to PLMN 24827. The arrows' directions represent the UE movement. The RSRP value at each step is written above the arrows.

Figure 29 Results of multi-PLMN test: (a) RSRP on steps from room 210 (LMT - 24701) to room 212 (TTU - 24827), (b) RSRP on steps from room 212 (TTU - 24827) to room 210 (LMT - 24701), (c) RSRQ on steps from room 210 (LMT - 24701) to room 212 (TTU - 24827), (d) RSRQ on steps from room 212 (TTU - 24827) to room 210 (LMT - 24701).

The results of the test are presented in Figure 29. It is visible that as we move away from the radio unit of a specific PLMN, its power decreases (e.g., RSRP and RSRQ), whereas the power of the other PLMN starts to increase. The results show at which step the PLMN (Cell ID) should be changed, that is when the handover should be performed. In the direction from room 210 to room 212, the change should be done at step 7, whereas in the opposite direction it should be done between the steps 5 and 6.

5.1.2 Multi-PLMN Interruption time

Switching from one PLMN to another results in service interruption due to dropping the first one (owing to insufficient signal power), then attaching to the other PLMN. In this section we present the measured interruption time as obtained from the Quectel RM500Q-GL module and the Nemo¹ measuring software.

The first test is a ping test, in which a 32 Byte packet size is used to test a local server in Tallinn. From Figure 30 it can be inferred that the average RTT ping time is ms (ranging from 23 to 27 ms, see details in the figure), which is comparable to that of the commercial Telia NSA network (27 ms) that covers the TTU campus. Next, the Nemo tool is used to analyze the ping results. Figure 31 shows that the average RTT is approximately 23 ms. .

The second test is the interruption time when the PLMN (i.e., moving from one PLMN to the other). Two types of tests are performed: the first is performed using the Quectel RM500Q-GL module and ping command (idle mode test). The second test is performed using Nemo while an active session is running. Figure 32 shows that in idle mode, it takes the UE approximately 1.4 s to connect to the second PLMN once it loses connectivity with the first one. Furthermore, it can be seen that most of the interruption time is due to establishing a new connection and registration to the new PLMN. Figure 33 and Figure 34 show the results of the Nemo measurements during active session. From Figure 33, it is clear that the UE loses connectivity at a specific point in time and then establishes a new connection with the new PLMN. From Figure 34, we can see that the UE was connected to the first PLMN, and then lost connectivity for approximately 4 s, in which the UE performed cell search measurements until it established a connection with the new PLMN.

Figure 30 Average, minimum, and maximum RTT of ping command using the Quectel RM500Q-GL.

¹ <https://www.keysight.com/in/en/solutions/5g/nemo-wireless-network-solutions.html>

Figure 31 The RTT of each performed ping command that is measured using the Nemo.

Figure 32 Inter-PLMN switching interruption time using the Quectel RM500Q-GL in idle mode.

Figure 33 Measured RSRP and interruption time during active session for inter-PLMN switching using Nemo.

EventId	Time	RRC direction	RRC sub...	RRC message name	RRC data
RRCSM	11:20:45.345	Uplink	DCCH	MeasurementReport	00 40 00 04 00 5D 33 13 E0 96 CB AD 7C DC
RRCSM	11:20:45.801	Uplink	DCCH	MeasurementReport	00 40 00 04 00 5D 3A E3 60 96 CB AF 78 BC
RRCSM	11:20:46.312	Uplink	DCCH	MeasurementReport	00 40 00 04 00 5D 22 C3 20 96 CB AC 7A CC
RRCSM	11:20:46.752	Uplink	DCCH	MeasurementReport	00 40 00 04 00 5D 22 C3 40 81 4B AC 76 CC
RRCSM	11:20:47.238	Uplink	DCCH	MeasurementReport	00 40 00 04 00 5D 42 F3 C0 96 CB AE 76 C8
RRCSM	11:20:47.733	Uplink	DCCH	MeasurementReport	00 40 00 04 00 5D 2A B3 20 96 CB AD 76 C0
RRCSM	11:20:48.204	Uplink	DCCH	MeasurementReport	00 40 00 04 00 5C F2 52 40 81 4B AF 78 E0
RRCSM	11:20:48.701	Uplink	DCCH	MeasurementReport	00 40 00 04 00 5C D9 D2 20 81 4B B2 7E FC
RRCSM	11:20:49.179	Uplink	DCCH	MeasurementReport	00 40 00 04 00 5C F1 B2 20 81 4B AD 7C D0
RRCSM	11:20:49.666	Uplink	DCCH	MeasurementReport	00 40 00 04 00 5D 02 02 40 81 4B B1 7E FC
RRCSM	11:20:50.132	Uplink	DCCH	MeasurementReport	00 40 00 04 00 5C A1 12 20 81 4B B5 81 24
RRCSM	11:20:50.755	Downlink	BCCH-BCH	MIB	35 86 14
RRCSM	11:20:50.890	Downlink	BCCH-SCH	SIB1	64 80 00 02 09 23 80 40 04 E2 40 00 01 0F EA B0 84 D0 24 00 00 2A 16 78 88 30 ...
RRCSM	11:20:50.892	Downlink	BCCH-BCH	MIB	35 AE 24
RRCSM	11:20:51.005	Downlink	BCCH-SCH	SIB1	6C 80 10 02 09 24 00 80 01 F9 4F 47 E5 36 BA 00 31 C1 04 00 42 04 30 1A 42 13 ...
RRCSM	11:20:52.846	Downlink	BCCH-BCH	MIB	4D 86 14
RRCSM	11:20:52.846	Downlink	BCCH-SCH	SIB1	64 80 00 02 09 23 80 40 04 E2 40 00 01 0F EA B0 84 D0 24 00 00 2A 16 78 88 30 ...
RRCSM	11:20:54.763	Downlink	BCCH-BCH	MIB	67 86 14
RRCSM	11:20:54.791	Downlink	BCCH-SCH	SIB1	64 80 00 02 09 23 80 40 04 E2 40 00 01 0F EA B0 84 D0 24 00 00 2A 16 78 88 30 ...
RRCSM	11:20:54.791	Uplink	CCCH	RRCSetupRequest	17 97 A5 0F FF A6
RRCSM	11:20:54.897	Downlink	CCCH	RRCSetup	20 40 04 0A 12 E0 05 80 08 8B D7 63 80 83 0F 30 03 E1 12 02 E8 3C DA 00 04 12 ...
RRCSM	11:20:54.897	Uplink	DCCH	RRCSetupComplete	10 C0 32 48 13 FF 80 46 93 DF 80 41 A4 0A B4 87 5F 80 10 48 80 02 FC 90 BE 1C ...
RRCSM	11:20:54.993	Downlink	DCCH	DLInformationTransfer	28 86 2F C0 5E 8B A6 38 82 CF C0 0A C0 60 40 00 04 3D 2F DA 13 F2 A1 8D 1D 9...
RRCSM	11:20:55.262	Uplink	DCCH	ULInformationTransfer	3A 0E 3F 01 4B 2E BC EF 0F 3F 00 2B 96 88 13 77 33 EA 1E 40 3C E6 E7 CF B7 BC ...
RRCSM	11:20:55.264	Downlink	DCCH	DLInformationTransfer	28 83 6F C0 66 76 7E 22 A0 0F C0 0B A0 40 60 5E 0E 1C 2A E4 46 C0 20 03 20 9E ...
RRCSM	11:20:55.264	Uplink	DCCH	ULInformationTransfer	3A 0B 3F 02 10 ED 98 B6 00 3F 00 2F 3B 80 04 9A BA 84 32 82 49 43 83 FA 80
RRCSM	11:20:55.357	Downlink	DCCH	SecurityModeCommand	20 09 10
RRCSM	11:20:55.357	Uplink	DCCH	SecurityModeComplete	28 00
RRCSM	11:20:55.389	Downlink	DCCH	RRCReconfiguration	00 AA A0 40 9A 01 A0 0A 05 E3 C0 9B 48 85 70 00 1E 00 04 D3 D0 14 01 08 00 10...
RRCSM	11:20:55.418	Uplink	DCCH	RRCReconfigurationComplete	08 00
RRCSM	11:20:55.418	Downlink	DCCH	DLInformationTransfer	28 88 6F C0 5D 86 DE 20 40 2F C0 08 40 20 2E E0 01 7E 48 5E E2 1F E0 11 BA 00 ...
RRCSM	11:20:55.418	Uplink	DCCH	ULInformationTransfer	3A 05 3F 01 60 8A A4 48 00 BF 00 21 80
RRCSM	11:20:55.453	Downlink	DCCH	DLInformationTransfer	28 83 AF C0 5B 0F BA F7 C0 4F C0 0A 88 60 30 08 A0 30 08 C4 28 E8 4A 00 50 00...

Figure 34 UE control messages during active session for inter-PLMN switching using Nemo.

5.1.3 Intra-gNB handover

This section is dedicated to verifying the 5G SA lab network at TTU can perform intra-gNB handover. As already mentioned, the lab infrastructure is different from that of the field (owing to the fact that this a small indoor network), and one of the main differences is that in the lab, only one BBU is used and both the radio units are connected to it; therefore, the setup is considered as a one gNB setup, and the handover is considered an intra-

gNB handover. This deployment has helped to perform a single network handover test, which was useful to verify the functionality of the handover itself, before testing inter-gNB handover.

Figure 35 depicts the handover interruption time moving from one PLMN to the other. It is observed that the interruption time is in the order of some ms, which is much lower than that of the PLMN switching, as expected. Handover preparation time is measured from the packet which contained "HandoverRequest" to the packet which contained "HandoverRequestAcknowledge". Handover interruption time is measured from the packet which contained "HandoverCommand" to the packet which contained "HandoverNotify". The packets were captured on 04.06. 2024 at 12:25-12:38 on AMF in the TTU core network. In the capture there are 2 handovers observed, one from Taltech to LMT and another from LMT back to Taltech.

Figure 35 Handover times from AMF packet capture, both directions.

The network was configured to test the intra-gNB handover in one direction from PLMN 24827 to PLMN 24701. The RAN logs that show the handover are presented below. Figure 36 shows the entire RAN log that was saved during the handover test, and Figure 37 show the part where the handover takes place. There are two highlighted parts in Figure 37, the red one is enlarged and presented in Figure 38, and the blue one is enlarged and presented in Figure 39. From Figure 38 we can see the measurement reports, in which the rsrp (i.e., the RSRP) of the serving cell (physCellId: 0) decreases until it reaches -119 dBm, while that of the neighbour cell (physCellId: 10) is -109 dBm. Figure 39 contains several information. Two important information are contained in the first and last columns of the figure. In the first column we can see the local unique cell identification number of the serving cell. It can be seen that this cell identification number has changed, which means that the handover has taken place and the UE is being served by another cell. From the last column, we can see the messages exchange between the UE, base station, and the core. We can see the RRC reconfiguration message that initiates the handover and the RRC reconfiguration completes the handover, as depicted earlier in Figure 4 in Section 3.

D3.11 Report on 5G Infrastructure Setup for CAM (final)

time	cell	ue trace id	ueRef	direction	type	message	parameters
2024-05-23 11:49:52.409000000	0x029A0D84CDE81	1016		RC --> CN	(NGAP)	UEContextReleaseComplete	amfUeNgapId:5114843043 ranUeNgapId:16790113 pimIdentity:248-27 gNBid:1 cellLocalId:1016 tac:001389H
2024-05-23 11:50:20.489000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	RRCSetupRequest	cause:mo-Data fiveG-TMSI:3758155597 ue-Identity:ng_5g_5_TMSI_Part1:59992730445
2024-05-23 11:50:20.490000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC --> UE	(RRC5G)	RRCSetup	logicalChannelIdentity:1 logicalChannelGroup:0 srb-Identity:1
2024-05-23 11:50:20.513000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC --> CN	(NGAP)	InitialUEMessage	ranUeNgapId:16790114 fiveG-TMSI:3758155597 pimIdentity:248-27 gNBid:1 cellLocalId:1016 tac:001389H amfUeNgapId:0000000010/B amfPointer:001101/B cause:mo-Data
2024-05-23 11:50:20.513000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	RRCSetupComplete	
2024-05-23 11:50:20.513000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC <-- UE	(NAS5GMM)	SGSNASMessageEncrypted	
2024-05-23 11:50:20.521000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC <-- CN	(NGAP)	InitialContextSetupRequest	amfUeNgapId:10374324416 ranUeNgapId:16790114 pimIdentity:248-27 sT:01/H amfRegionId:11111111/B amfSetID:0000000010/B amfPointer:001101/B PDUSessionType:ipv4 s...
2024-05-23 11:50:20.521000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC --> UE	(RRC5G)	UERadioAccessCapabilityInformation	
2024-05-23 11:50:20.521000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC --> UE	(RRC5G)	UE-RR-Capability	
2024-05-23 11:50:20.521000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC --> UE	(RRC5G)	SecurityModeCommand	
2024-05-23 11:50:20.521000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC --> UE	(RRC5G)	RRCCReconfiguration	logicalChannelIdentity:2 logicalChannelIdentity:3 drb_Identity:1 logicalChannelGroup:0 logicalChannelGroup:5 srb-Identity:2 ssbFrequency:632736 _NR_eventA2 _NR_eventA3 me...
2024-05-23 11:50:20.521000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	SecurityModeComplete	
2024-05-23 11:50:20.548000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	RRCCReconfigurationComplete	
2024-05-23 11:50:20.548000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC --> CN	(NGAP)	InitialContextSetupResponse	amfUeNgapId:10374324416 ranUeNgapId:16790114 qosFlowIdentifier:8 gTP-TED:880C0000/H
2024-05-23 11:50:20.548000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC --> UE	(RRC5G)	DLInformationTransfer	
2024-05-23 11:50:20.548000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC <-- UE	(NAS5GMM)	SGSNASMessageEncrypted	
2024-05-23 11:50:25.570000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	MeasurementReport	measId:2(NR_A3) physCellId:0 ServingMOList:{rsrp:-114,rsrq:-16.0,sinr:-5.0} physCellId:182 NeighCells:{rsrp:-107,rsrq:-12.0,sinr:5.5}
2024-05-23 11:50:26.113000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	MeasurementReport	measId:2(NR_A3) physCellId:0 ServingMOList:{rsrp:-115,rsrq:-19.0,sinr:-10.5} physCellId:182 NeighCells:{rsrp:-110,rsrq:-15.0,sinr:-4.5}
2024-05-23 11:50:26.296000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	MeasurementReport	measId:2(NR_A3) physCellId:0 ServingMOList:{rsrp:-119,rsrq:-20.0,sinr:-10.0} physCellId:10 NeighCells:{rsrp:-109,rsrq:-12.5,sinr:5.5}
2024-05-23 11:50:26.304000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1016		RC --> UE	(RRC5G)	RRCCReconfiguration	logicalChannelIdentity:1 logicalChannelIdentity:2 logicalChannelIdentity:3 drb_Identity:1 logicalChannelGroup:0 logicalChannelGroup:5 srb-Identity:1 srb-Id...
2024-05-23 11:50:26.373000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1018		RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	RRCCReconfigurationComplete	
2024-05-23 11:50:26.453000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1018		RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	ULInformationTransfer	
2024-05-23 11:50:26.453000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1018		RC <-- UE	(NAS5GMM)	SGSNASMessageEncrypted	
2024-05-23 11:50:26.453000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1018		RC --> CN	(NGAP)	InitialUEMessage	amfUeNgapId:10374324416 ranUeNgapId:16790114 pimIdentity:247-01 gNBid:1 cellLocalId:1018 tac:001389H
2024-05-23 11:50:26.463000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1018		RC <-- CN	(NGAP)	DownlinkNASTransport	amfUeNgapId:10374324416 ranUeNgapId:16790114 sT:01/H
2024-05-23 11:50:26.463000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1018		RC <-- UE	(NAS5GMM)	SGSNASMessageEncrypted	
2024-05-23 11:50:26.463000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1018		RC --> UE	(RRC5G)	DLInformationTransfer	
2024-05-23 11:50:26.463000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1018		RC --> UE	(RRC5G)	ULInformationTransfer	
2024-05-23 11:50:26.510000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1018		RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	ULInformationTransfer	
2024-05-23 11:50:26.510000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1018		RC <-- UE	(NAS5GMM)	SGSNASMessageEncrypted	
2024-05-23 11:50:26.510000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1018		RC --> CN	(NGAP)	UplinkNASTransport	amfUeNgapId:10374324416 ranUeNgapId:16790114 pimIdentity:247-01 gNBid:1 cellLocalId:1018 tac:001389H
2024-05-23 11:50:26.510000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1018		RC --> UE	(NAS5GMM)	SGSNASMessageEncrypted	
2024-05-23 11:50:47.847000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1018		RC --> CN	(NGAP)	UEContextReleaseRequest	amfUeNgapId:10374324416 ranUeNgapId:16790114 cause:radioNetwork-user-inactivity
2024-05-23 11:50:47.847000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1018		RC <-- CN	(NGAP)	UEContextReleaseComplete	amfUeNgapId:10374324416 ranUeNgapId:16790114 cause:radioNetwork-release-due-to-ngran-generated-reason
2024-05-23 11:50:47.847000000	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	1018		RC --> UE	(RRC5G)	RRCCRelease	

Figure 36 Ran log recorded during the handover test.

1016	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	MeasurementReport	measId:2(NR_A3) physCellId:0 ServingMOList:{rsrp:-114,rsrq:-16.0,sinr:-5.0} physCellId:182 NeighCells:{rsrp:-107,rsrq:-12.0,sinr:5.5}
1016	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	MeasurementReport	measId:2(NR_A3) physCellId:0 ServingMOList:{rsrp:-115,rsrq:-19.0,sinr:-10.5} physCellId:182 NeighCells:{rsrp:-110,rsrq:-15.0,sinr:-4.5}
1016	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	MeasurementReport	measId:2(NR_A3) physCellId:0 ServingMOList:{rsrp:-119,rsrq:-20.0,sinr:-10.0} physCellId:10 NeighCells:{rsrp:-109,rsrq:-12.5,sinr:5.5}
1016	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	RC --> UE	(RRC5G)	RRCCReconfiguration	logicalChannelIdentity:1 logicalChannelIdentity:2 logicalChannelIdentity:3 drb_Identity:1 logicalChannelGroup:0 logicalChan...
1018	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	RRCCReconfigurationComplete	
1018	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	ULInformationTransfer	

Figure 37 The part (taken from Figure 36) that shows the handover procedure. The red rectangle is shown in Figure 38 while the blue one is shown in Figure 39.

measId:2(NR_A3) physCellId:0 ServingMOList:{rsrp:-114,rsrq:-16.0,sinr:-5.0} physCellId:182 NeighCells:{rsrp:-107,rsrq:-12.0,sinr:5.5}
measId:2(NR_A3) physCellId:0 ServingMOList:{rsrp:-115,rsrq:-19.0,sinr:-10.5} physCellId:182 NeighCells:{rsrp:-110,rsrq:-15.0,sinr:-4.5}
measId:2(NR_A3) physCellId:0 ServingMOList:{rsrp:-119,rsrq:-20.0,sinr:-10.0} physCellId:10 NeighCells:{rsrp:-109,rsrq:-12.5,sinr:5.5}

Figure 38 The last measurement report shows that the signal quality of the serving cell is worse than that of the neighbor cell, thus triggering the handover.

1016	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	MeasurementReport
1016	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	MeasurementReport
1016	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	MeasurementReport
1016	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	RC --> UE	(RRC5G)	RRCCReconfiguration
1018	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	RRCCReconfigurationComplete
1018	0x9A5A0DA0E85AE804	RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	ULInformationTransfer

Figure 39 The serving cell identification number is changed from 1016 to 1018, indicating that the handover has been successful and that the serving cell has been changed.

5.2 Tests and verification results from the field-trial site (Valga-Valka)

This part provides the field verification test results. The verification was performed in the Valga-Valka cross-border sites.

5.2.1 Cross-border coverage measurements

First, it is needed to verify that the sites provide adequate coverage, especially to provide the cross-border handover. In this part we present the equipment used to obtain the measurements, and the setup and then the coverage measurements itself in Valga-Valka border crossing.

Coverage was measured with the Rohde & Schwarz R&S TSME6 scanner device, shown in Figure 40, as this device has good accuracy (± 1 dB) and can measure multiple CellID's and frequency channels concurrently. Each radio in

the coverage area has a unique Physical Cell Identity (PCI), for example, the LMT base station in Valka has a PCI that represents the radio connected to the TTU core. For the measurements, the RSRP of the different PCI were scanned, measured and logged to assess the coverage.

Figure 40 R&S TSME6 scanner device.

A dedicated software, namely the Rohde & Schwarz R&S ROMES4 software was used to control the TSME6 scanner and log measurement results, see Figure 41.

Figure 41 R&S ROMES4 measurement software tool used together with the TSME6 scanner. The RSRP of different PCI is measured.

Regarding the trial's setup, equipment was mounted on a car. The car moved back and forth between Valga and Valka. Specifically, the scanner's antenna was installed on a car's rooftop and a GPS device was used to log measurement positions, see Figure 42.

Figure 42 Scanner and GPS device antennas.

Figure 43 and Figure 44 show the RSRP signal level measurements when driving from Estonia (Valga gNB) to Latvia (Valka gNB) and vice versa, respectively. Based on these measurement results, the network parameters for the cross-border handover will be defined for the trials.

Figure 43 Measured signal level RSRP of Valga gNB, while driving from Estonia to Latvia.

Figure 44 Measured signal level RSRP of Valka gNB, while driving from Latvia to Estonia.

Figure 45 shows measurements from both gNB on the same map view. Note that Latvian and Estonian gNBs are using different frequency channels; therefore, the cross-border handover will be an inter-frequency handover.

Figure 45 Measured signals levels RSRP from both gNBs in a single map view.

5.2.2 Multi-PLMN interruption time

In this section, the tests that were performed at the TTU lab are repeated at the Estonian-Latvian border. The PLMN change verification test route is illustrated in Figure 46. In Valga (Estonia) the network with the name “Taltech” is provided by Telia BS and in Valka (Latvia) the network with the name LMT is provided by LMT BS. A ping test is used, in which a 32-byte packet size is transmitted to a local server in Tallinn. At the starting point ("Test start point" in the figure), the UE is registered to the first network (i.e., PLMN), and a PDU session is activated. The vehicle that contains the UE moves toward the endpoint ("Test end point" in the figure), while the AT command (AT+QENG="servingcell") is used periodically every 10 ms. The test is repeated in both directions, as shown in the figure. The results are shown in Figure 47. The average RTT in Estonia is 25 or 27 ms (without and with EMBB slice, respectively), which is comparable to the TTU lab results. The average RTT is longer in Telia's commercial NSA network (36 ms), and in Latvia, it is 84 ms or 85 ms (without and with EMBB slice) due to delay of the transport network.

Figure 46 The cross-border field trial route, from Estonia to Latvia (blue line) and vice-versa (orange line).

Figure 47 Average, minimum, and maximum round trip time of ping command using the Quectel RM500Q-GL.

5.2.3 Inter-gNB handover results

Inter-PLMN handover (inter-gNB and inter-frequency) is successfully tested in the field (Valga-Valka). The handover messages work on the core level as seen from the AMF logs Figure 48. This figure shows a number of HO required packets collected during field trial measurements with the 5G modem. The actual interruption time is a combination of uplinkRANStatusTransfer (from source gNB to AMF) and downlinkRANStatusTransfer (from AMF to target gNB) messages. On average, we obtained 46 ms as interruption time, which is a very impressive result (obtained after several RAN optimizations).

To specify the interruption time at the RAN, as per Figure 4 (presented earlier in Section 3), the interruption time is between HO Request Acknowledge and Path Switch request messages. Figure 49 shows the handover results from the RAN logs (as an example), the actual interruption time is 15 ms. This is calculated based on the timestamp values between HO Request Acknowledge (16:34:50:54xx) and Path Switch request (16:34:50:69xx) messages. Please note that the interruption times at the 5G SA core (46ms) and at the 5G SA RAN (15ms) are different because they are measured with different types of messages at their respective points. This allows us to be able to have a deeper understanding of the interruption times at different points of the 5G network.

Figure 48 AMF logs for HANDOVER messages.

D3.11 Report on 5G Infrastructure Setup for CAM (final)

2024-06-09 16:34:50.539910525	42868	0xEB8914930AE7EB26		RC <-- TGNB	(XNAP)	HandoverRequest
2024-06-09 16:34:50.539910525	42868	0xEB8914930AE7EB26		RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	HandoverPreparationInformation
2024-06-09 16:34:50.539910525	42868	0xEB8914930AE7EB26		RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	UE-NR-Capability
2024-06-09 16:34:50.547572392	42868	0xEB8914930AE7EB26		RC --> UE	(RRC5G)	DRX-Config
2024-06-09 16:34:50.547761868	42868	0xEB8914930AE7EB26		RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	DRX-Config
2024-06-09 16:34:50.548256155	42868	0xEB8914930AE7EB26		RC --> TGNB	(XNAP)	HandoverRequestAcknowledge
2024-06-09 16:34:50.548256155	42868	0xEB8914930AE7EB26		UE --> RC	(RRC5G)	HandoverCommand
2024-06-09 16:34:50.561035280	42868	0xEB8914930AE7EB26		RC <-- TGNB	(XNAP)	SNStatusTransfer
2024-06-09 16:34:50.689736121	42868	0xEB8914930AE7EB26		RC <-- UE	(RRC5G)	RRCReconfigurationComplete
2024-06-09 16:34:50.691302458	42868	0xEB8914930AE7EB26		RC --> CN	(NGAP)	PathSwitchRequest
2024-06-09 16:34:50.741127492	42868	0xEB8914930AE7EB26		RC <-- CN	(NGAP)	PathSwitchRequestAcknowledge
2024-06-09 16:34:50.741255371	42868	0xEB8914930AE7EB26		RC --> TGNB	(XNAP)	UEContextRelease
2024-06-09 16:34:55.625171631	42868	0xEB8914930AE7EB26		RC --> CN	(NGAP)	UEContextReleaseRequest
2024-06-09 16:34:55.797205405	42868	0xEB8914930AE7EB26		RC <-- CN	(NGAP)	UEContextReleaseCommand

Figure 49 RAN log recorded during the handover test

6 Conclusions

Task T3.1 and deliverable D3.11 presented the final technical project architecture of the 5G-ROUTES project. In this deliverable, modifications performed on the previous version of the PA were highlighted. The main modification is the inclusion and use of the inter-PLMN technical solution in the PA. The inter-PLMN was presented, along with its impact on various infrastructure components.

Furthermore, the deployed infrastructure is presented, and its operation is verified. The infrastructure components are the core, UEs, and RAN sites. An Ericsson small-core solution is used in this project. The core, which is located at TTU, was presented in the deliverable. Moreover, the core capabilities such as slicing and positioning services were also presented. Logs showing the operation of the core and its various services were provided. The UE and RAN node descriptions were provided in the deliverable.

The transport network connects the sites in Valga, Valka, and Bikernieki to the TTU core over an optical fibre network. A diagram illustrating the transport network is presented, along with an explanation of the main operation. The details of the sites were previously provided in deliverable D3.1. In the current deliverable D3.11, the final selected parameters are reported in addition to any changes to the sites.

Finally, the results and logs of the conducted lab and the cross-border field verification tests and measurements are presented. These verifications comprise the results and parameters that show that the network (including the inter-PLMN handover solution) is operational.

As the next steps, the operational 5G network infrastructure provided in this deliverable will further be used for integrating the multi-domain CAM platform (D3.7). Also, the edge network deployment and its integration will be explained in D3.7. Grounding on the terrestrial use case experiments descriptions (see Section 6 of D4.1), the 5G infrastructure described in this deliverable will be put to use for conducting the field trials as per the test procedures described in Section 7 and Section 8 of D4.1. Subsequently, the cross-border field trials results will be presented in D4.5 and subsequently the performance evaluation and lessons learned in D4.8.

7 References

- [1] Quectel, "https://www.quectel.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Quectel_RM500Q-GL_5G_Specification_V1.3.pdf".
- [2] 5Gcroco, "Deliverable D4.3 Final Phase Trial Execution Report and Analysis of 5GCroCo KPIs," 2022.
- [3] 5GMOBIX, "D6.3 Plan and Preliminary Report on the Standardisation and Spectrum Allocation Needs," 2021.
- [4] 3GPP, "Digital cellular telecommunications system (Phase 2+); Universal Mobile Telecommunications System (UMTS); Handover requirements between UTRAN and GERAN or other radio systems (3GPP TS 22.129 version 8.1.0 Release 8)".

Annex I: AT commands response format

Response format of AT+QENG="servingcell":

<state>	UE state: „SEARCH“ - seaching, „NOCONN“ – registered and idle
„NR5G-SA“	„NR5G-SA“
<duplex_mode>	„TDD“
<MCC>	Mobile Country Code – 248 (Estonia) or 247 (Latvia)
<MNC>	Mobile Network Code – 27 (Taltech) or 1 (LMT)
<cellID>	Cell ID
<PCID>	Physical cell ID
<TAC>	tracking area
<ARFCN>	Absolute Radio-Frequency Channel Number
<band>	frequency band
<NR_DL_bandwidth>	Bandwidth of NR in DL
<RSRP>	Reference Signal Received Power
<RSRQ>	Reference Signal Received Quality
<SINR>	Signal-to-interference plus Noise Ratio
<scs>	NR subcarrier spacing
<srxlev>	Reception level value